

FOREST ECOLOGY

AGROCHEMICAL, PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS DISTURBED BY ANTHROPOGENIC-TECHNICAL EFFECTS IN THE TERRITORY OF GARADAGH DISTRICT

*Bagirova B.,
Bagirov H.,
Khalilov F.,
Hashimova A.*

*AR MSE Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry,
leading scientific worker, scientific worker*

Abstract

The research works were carried out in the contaminated soils in the oil and gas production area of Garadagh district. Soil samples were taken from the area based on the coordinates. Analyzes were carried out in the laboratory to determine the mechanical, physico-chemical and agrochemical properties of the collected soil samples.

Keywords: anthropogenic-technical effects, granulometric composition, physical-chemical properties of soil, agrochemical properties of soil, sand, silt, clay

One of the global problems of the modern era is environmental protection. In this regard, oil pollution of the biosphere is of particular importance. Despite the observance of safety rules in the process of oil extraction, transportation and processing, soil pollution is inevitable. This, in turn, affects the disturbance of the ecological balance, changes in the structure of biocenoses, and the intensity of soil cultivation processes.

The experience in the field of elimination of environmental pollution with petroleum products shows that an objective assessment of the polluted ecosystem is an important condition.

Absheron Peninsula is one of the regions in our republic where the soil cover is more exposed to anthropogenic pressures. The Absheron Peninsula is at the forefront of the development of the oil industry apart from being the most developed economic region of our country. The crude oil produced here is a valuable raw material for obtaining various types of high-quality oil products [1, 2].

For the first time, many scientists were engaged in research on the fertility of oil-contaminated soils in Azerbaijan [2, 3, 4, 5, 7].

Effective use of existing land resources, protection of fertility, preparation of a system of necessary measures for the return to use of lands that are conventionally considered unsuitable today, in particular, determination of ways to eliminate the limiting factors that lead to the degradation of soil cover are carried out in the world, including in the Republic of Azerbaijan (ecological, agrotechnical, reclamation, agrochemical, microbiological, etc.) is one of the prospective directions of research.

Restoration of oil-contaminated areas by the method of phytomelioration, that is, a system of measures applied to radically change the natural conditions of the area by the vegetation.

As a phytoremediation measure in oil-polluted areas, it is recommended to plant perennial grasses that are resistant to oil to adapt the vegetation to the conditions due to the agrotechnical and meliorative measures implemented in the area [6].

In this context, reclamation measures are applied in Canada, Russia, Norway and other countries.

It is considered appropriate to use perennial plantings for phytomelioration of soils in oil-contaminated areas in the conditions of Absheron in Azerbaijan.

Research methodology. The research works were carried out in the contaminated soils in the oil and gas production area of Garadagh district. Soil samples were taken from the area based on the coordinates. Analyzes were carried out in the laboratory to determine the mechanical, physico-chemical and agrochemical properties of the collected soil samples. All laboratory analyzes were performed by the following methods, which are currently the most widely used: granulometric composition - N.A. Kachinsky; absorbed Ca and Mg – D.V. Ivanov; absorbed Na – Hedroys; common humus I.V. Tyurin; pH-potentiometer (pH-meter); absorbed ammonia – D.P. Konev; activated phosphorus - B.P. Machigin; exchangeable potassium – was determined by the P.B. Protasov method.

Analysis and discussion. The result of the analysis of the mechanical composition of the soil in the samples taken from the layers of 0-30, 30-60, 60-90 cm in the soil samples is reflected in the table below.

Table 1

Granulometric composition of soils

Sample №	Depth, cm	1-0,25	0,25-0,05	0,05-0,01	0,01-0,005	0,005-0,001	< 0,001	< 0,01
1	0-30 sm	0.06	19.14	22.00	12.80	29.20	16.80	58.80
2	30-60 sm	0.32	44.48	49.60	2.80	2.00	0.80	5.60
3	60-90 sm	0.35	24.05	30.00	12.40	21.20	12.00	45.60
		Sand			Silt		Clay	

As can be seen from table 1, the soils of the area belong to the type of mechanically light granular soils. Water permeability is average.

Table 2

Absorbed bases in irrigated light grey-brown soils

Depth, cm	Ca	Mg	Na	Sum of absorbed bases, (SAB), mg-eq	Ca	Mg	Na
	mg-eq				Percentage from SAB		
0-25	12.2	18.0	2.4	32.6	37.43	55.21	7.36
25-50	14.0	13.0	2.2	29.2	47.95	44.52	7.53
50-75	12.9	9.2	3.2	25.3	50.99	35.4	12.60
75-100	16.5	14.5	2.6	33.6	49.11	43.15	7.74

As can be seen from table 2 the SAB is 32.6-33.6 mg.eq in the irrigated light grey-brown soils of the Garadagh district. 12.2-16.5 mg-eq Ca, 14.5-18.0 mg-eq Mg, 2.4-2.6 mg-eq Na fall on 100 g of soil in the crop

and sub-crop layers in these soils. The percentages occupied by Ca, Mg and Na are, respectively, 37.43-49.11; 35.4-55.21; 7.36-12.60%.

Table 3

Agrochemical properties of soils

Depth, cm	pH	Humus %	Absorbed NH ₃ mg/kg	Activated phosphorus, mg/kg	Exchangeable potassium, mg/kg
0-20	7.6	1.86	19.4	23.3	190.4
20-40	7.7	1.47	15.9	21.9	175.0
40-60	7.75	1.20	14.1	16.6	135.0
60-80	7.89	0.67	12.3	10.7	113.3
80-100	8.3	0.53	10.6	5.7	113.3

As a result of the research, it was found that the pH is 7.6-8.3, as can be seen from the analyzes of the agrochemical characteristics of the irrigated light grey-brown soils of the Garadagh district. Humus is 1.86% in the 0-20 cm layer of the soil, and it decreases to 0.53%

in the depth of 80-100 cm in the soils of the research area. According to the profile, absorbed ammonia in these soils is 10.6-19.4 mg/kg; activated phosphorus 5.7-23.3 mg/kg; exchangeable potassium varies between 113.3-190.4 mg/kg. (Table 3).

Figure

Conclusion

1. The irrigated light grey-brown soils of the Garadagh district mechanically belong to the type of light granular soils. Water permeability is average.

2. In the irrigated light grey-brown soils of the Garadagh district, the SAB is 32.6-33.6 mg.eq. in these soils, 12.2-16.5 mg-eq Ca, 14.5-18.0 mg-eq Mg, 2.4-2.6 mg-eq Na fall on 100 g of soil in the crop and sub-crop layers. The percentages occupied by Ca, Mg and Na are, respectively, 37.43-49.11; 35.4-55.21; 7.36-12.60%.

3. As a result of the research, it was found that the pH is 7.6-8.3, as can be seen from the analysis of the agrochemical characteristics of the irrigated light grey-brown soils of the Garadag district. Humus is 1.86% in the 0-20 cm layer of the soil, and it decreases to 0.53% in the depth of 80-100 cm in the soils of the research area. According to the profile, absorbed ammonia in these soils is 10.6-19.4 mg/kg; water-soluble phosphorus 5.7-23.3 mg/kg; exchangeable potassium varies between 113.3-190.4 mg/kg.

References

1. Aslanov H.G. Environmental characteristics of oil-contaminated soils in Absheron. "Problems of seismic stable construction and architecture" BK materials. Baku, 2005, pp. 386-389.
2. Babayev M.P. Agrosoil classification of anthropogenic soils. Azerbaijan. Proceedings of the Land Society, Volume VII. Baku, 2001, p. 19-28
3. Mammadov G.Sh., Hakimova N.F. Environmental indicators of oil-contaminated soils on the Absheron Peninsula. Materials of the conference on "Scientific Assurance of Land Reform" in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku 2002, p. 326-330
4. Mammadov G.Sh., Hakimova N.F. An ecological fertility model of oil-contaminated soils. Baku, "Science" 2003, 50 p.
5. Yagubov G.S. AR ways of recultivation of man-made disturbed lands. Baku 2003, 205 p.
6. Yagubov G.Sh., Ahmadov V.A., Shikhaliyev A.O. Some characteristics of man-made disturbed soils of the Siyazan massif. Works of the Society of Soil Scientists of Azerbaijan. Volume VII. Baku. 2001. pp. 40-42.
7. Mammadov P. T. Agrophysical properties of soils of the Azerbaijan SSR. Baku. Elm, 1989. 244 p.